

CONSEQUENCE OF OPPOSITION PARTIES IN JAPAN

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Abstract

Japan has espoused unitary democratic parliamentary system and constitutional monarchy since 1947. The parliament of Japan called 'Diet', comprised of two houses, the House of Representatives and House of Councilors. House of Representatives is an important house in comparison to House of Councilors in terms of its working and composition. Political parties in Japan, unlike other democratic countries, contest election and send their elected representatives to the Diet. The majority of seats of a political party leads the formation of government to implement its policies. Political parties with short of majority sit in the capacity of opposition in the house, participates in rule making and wait for the next election.

Aim of the paper:

The major aim of this paper to discuss the nature opposition politics in Japan and their relevance in the political system. Japan has large number of political parties, only few has maintained the credibility and existed for long. The paper would deal with the opposition political parties and their character to uphold the ethics of political setup in Japan.

Introduction:

Japanese systematic political development began with Meiji era in 1867 and five charter of oath were adopted to launch Japan as a strong, committed and friendly country in the world. The Japanese political system adopted

the parliamentary form of government, based on the idea of Prussian system under the direct control on monarchy. The adaptation of the constitution of empire of Japan in 1889, provided the house of representatives to initiate laws under the supervision of the Emperor. The scope of political parties conceptualized towards the in the end of nineteenth century, during the stronghold of Meiji days in Japan.

After World War II, Japan undergone with drastic change in its functioning of political system. New Japanese constitution was adopted in May of 1947, after the defeat in World War II, and the electoral politics began to invite various ideologies, which supported Japan to be a democratic country with pride and advancement. Japanese first general elections for the House of Representatives were held in January 1949, in which Democratic Liberal Party won the majority of seats and Democratic Party secured the second highest seats with opposition status. After that moment, various changes took place in the term of philosophies of political parties. Nonetheless, the faction and dissidents among the political parties have invented many smaller parties with the opposition distinction.

The merger of Liberal and Democrats in 1955 (called 1955 setup or system) have led to the formation of Liberal Democratic Party (LDP), which eventually ruled Japan for almost five decades with little changes (a coalition government in 1970s). The performance of opposition parties in these years were unremarkable. The formation of LDP with strong nationalism and liberal conservatism, has dominated the politics of Japan. The 1955 setup was the 'one-and-a-half party system', refers to the party system in Japan from 1955 to 1993, in which the LDP repeatedly held the majority in the both houses of Diet, while the major opposition the Japan Socialist Party (JSP, now Social Democratic Party: SDP), was not much capable to form as an alternative. Japan under the '1955 setup', witnessed the economic miracle, then again the dominance of the ruling party in the Diet, with a linking between the bureaucracy and the business part. Due to a series of LDP scandals and the 1992 and the burst of Japanese asset price bubble, LDP lost its majority in the House of Representatives in

the general election which was held in July 1993.
Major Opposition Parties in Japan: Past and Present

After the first general election of 1949, the main political party emerged as the opposition, was the Japanese Communist Party as leftist inkling party, led by Kyuichi Tokuda. Japanese Socialist Party existed in between 1948 to 1955. Socialist and social democratic parties have been active in Japan, under various names, party was originally known as the Social Democratic Party of Japan (SDPJ), and was formed in 1945, after the World War II. The conflict inside the party and emerged factions of the right and the left, the SDP continued with its agenda with socialist approach.

The party became the largest political party in the first general election under the Constitution of Japan in 1947 (143 of 466 seats), and a government was formed by Tetsu Katayama, forming a coalition with the Democratic Party and the Citizens' Cooperation Party. However, due to the rebellion of Marxists in the party, the Katayama government was lost. The party continued the coalition with the Democrats under prime minister Hitoshi Ashida; nonetheless the cabinet was engulfed by the Showa Denko scandal within seven months, allowing Shigeru Yoshida and the Liberal Party to lead the government. In the period following the end of the Second World War, the Socialists played a key role in the conscripting of the new Japanese constitution, adding reform based articles related to concerns such as health, wellbeing and working circumstances. The party was divided in 1950-51 into the Rightist Socialist Party of Japan, comprising of Socialists who supported more to the political center, and the Leftist Socialist Party of Japan, which was formed by the left and Marxist-Socialists. The two socialist parties were combined in 1955, reunifying and recreating the Social Democratic Party of Japan.

Whereas, Japanese Communist Party (JCP), which was founded in 1922, had chance to participate in the new political process of Japan after World War II. The JCP is one of the largest non-ruling communist parties in the world. It advocates the formation of society

based on socialism, democracy, peace and opposition to hostility. It proposes to achieve its objectives by working within a democratic framework. The party does not support violent revolution, and firmly defend the Article 9 of the Japanese constitution due to its opposition of the re-militarization of Japan. The JCP wish to terminate the Japan–United States military alliance and the dismantle of all the US military bases in Japan.

Komeito (instituted by non-politically active members of Soka Gakkai) had an influence in Japanese politics since 1993. Prior to 1993, the Komeito was in opposition. The party had professed with the people center politics, founded on a humanitarianism.

Nationally, party proposal includes the limitation of central government and bureaucracy, and the increased transparency. Komeito, primarily began as the Political Federation for Clean Government in 1961, however, held its opening concord as Komeito in November 1964. The three characters Ko, Mei, To has its meaning as public/government, light/brightness and political party, which altogether donates 'justice or fairness'. Komeito often joined in government formation, though 1993-94, it supported the anti-LDP (main ruling political party since 1955) campaign and formed coalition government. The party split in 1994 and in 1998 merged with New Peace Party (NPP), and formed 'New Komeito'. It joined the permanent coalition with LDP and managed the satisfactory vote share in the elections for the Diet in 2003 elections and afterward.

Democratic Socialist Party (DSP) was established in 1960 by a breakaway faction (led by Suehiro Nishio) of the Japan Socialist Party. It was fabricated by the members of the former Rightist Socialist Party of Japan, a moderate democratic socialist faction that existed between 1948 and 1955. The DSP supported the construction of a welfare state, opposed totalitarianism, and strongly backed the Japan-US alliance. This made the pro-US and anti-communist alliance within the LDP continued to have majority in Diet. It derived much of its financial and organizational support from the labor confederation.

The DSP was dissolved in 1994 to join

the New Frontier Party. In 1996, the Japan Socialist Party was transformed into the Social Democratic Party (SDP). Two years later, in 1998, the New Frontier Party (NFP) dissolved and mostly former DSP members ultimately joined the Democratic Party of Japan, and on 27 March 2016 the DPJ merged with the Japan Innovation Party (JIP) and Vision of Reform to form the Democratic Party.

Recent Trends:

In 2014 general elections in Japan, LDP emerged victorious with huge majority and formed the coalition government with its partner Komeito and this election was observed as the lowest voter turnout in Japanese history. DPJ was the main opposition party along with, JCP. Nonetheless, other smaller political parties got attention after sharing remarkable vote percentage. Innovation Party (formed in September 2014), Party for Future Generations (formed in August 2014), People's Life Party (formed in December 2012), showed their presence in the House of Representatives of Japan. Innovation Party merged with DPJ to form the Democratic Party in March 2016, Party for Future Generation was dissolved in November 2018, and the People's Life Party changed its name in 2016 as 'Liberal Party', which merged with DPJ in late April of 2019.

Moreover, various other smaller opposition political emerged after 2017 general elections in Japan. The ruling LDP emerged as a single largest party and formed the government with its natural ally, Komeito. Constitutional Democratic Party of Japan (CDP) emerged as a new entrant and managed better vote sharing in comparison to Social Democratic Party (SDP) and the JCP. The CDP was formed in October 2017 and exists presently. The new entrants were the New Party Daichi (formed in August 2005) and the Happiness Realization Party (formed in May 2009) in general elections of October 2017; these are smallest in vote sharing as compare to CDP, SDP and JCP, however, they have increased their base in Japan.

Conclusion:

Japanese political system has experienced radical changes since 1993, when ruling LDP lost its majority and coalition era began. All the opposition parties emerged, are either centrist

or rightist dissenters' breakaways or factions. The sensitivity of politics in Japan is solely depend on the awareness common people, who participate during the elections and try to choose better option available for the voting. Opposition parties had the credibility of their agenda, nevertheless, ruling LDP has the largest backup from its supporters in all over Japan. Only fundamental reform in opposition parties would never be helpful for getting maximum number of seats in election. The streamlining and people oriented policies of the opposition political parties would be helpful to perform better in the elections near future.

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